

Condensation of β -Naphthyl Glyoxal Hydrate with Aromatic Amines

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Anils of β -naphthyl glyoxal were obtained by condensing with aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *m*-nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline, α -naphthylamine, β -naphthylamine and *p*-dimethylaminocaniline.

Derivatives prepared for characterising them were 2:4 DNP semicarbazones and oximes.

The structure of the anils was found by running the IR spectra of the anils in the KBr medium. From the stretching frequencies of $>C=O$ and azomethine group $-CH=N$ as well as from the nature of the derivatives obtained, the structures were proposed.

Anils derived from glyoxal and aromatic amines have not been investigated comprehensively. Few references are available on the anils derived from glyoxals and aromatic amines. The only reference worth mentioning is that of Krohnke and Gross¹ who synthesised *para* dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal to investigate bathochromic effect in the compound in presence of Lewis acids and silica gel.

Recently anils derived from phenyl-glyoxal-hydrate and primary aromatic amines have been reported². In the present communication investigation on the synthesis of anils obtained from β -naphthylglyoxalhydrate are reported. The methods recommended by the authors are employed in their preparation except in the case of the anil, *p*-dimethyl amino anil of β -naphthylglyoxal nitrile where a different route³ has to be used. These anils have been characterised from their 2:4, dinitro phenylhydrazones, semicarbazones and oximes.

Preparation of Anils: The anils listed in Table I were prepared by refluxing on water bath equimolar quantities of β -naphthylglyoxalhydrate⁴ and corresponding amines in a mixture of glacial acetic acid and ethanol (1:6 v/v) except in the case of *p*-dimethyl⁵ amino anil of β -naphthylglyoxal in which condensation was carried out in 70% ethanol at room temperature. On cooling a yellow oil was obtained which was difficult to crystallise. The following procedure was, therefore, adopted. The oily mass was dissolved in a minimum quantity of benzene and chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. Petroleum ether (60-80°), benzene, chloroform and their mixtures were used as the eluants. Most of the fractions were found to be greasy except that from chloroform which afforded a solid mass on evaporating the solvent. The left over was charcolised and rechromatographed but even then solid could not be obtained. The fraction obtained from chloroform was crystallised from hot methanol. The anils reported above are soluble in benzene, xylene, toluene, acetone, chloroform and acetonitrile but are practically insoluble in water.

1. F. Krohnke and K. F. Gross., *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, **92**, 36.
2. W. U. Malik, D. R. Gupta and C. L. Taploo, *J. Chem. Eng. Data.*, 1966, **210**, 11.
3. F. Krohnke and E. Borner., *Ber. dtsh. Chem. Ges.* 1936., **2012**, 69.
4. L. N. Goldyrev and I. Ya Postovaskli, *J. Gen. Chem.* (U. S.S.S. R.), 1940, **10**, 39-42.
5. D. A. Shirley, "Preparation of Organic Intermediates", p-9, 1951, John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York.

Preparation of p-Dimethylamino anil of β -Naphthyl glyoxal nitrile: Pyridinium iodide of β -naphthyl methyl ketone was synthesised by the interaction of iodine with β -naphthyl methyl ketone in presence of pyridine⁶. 0.80 gm. of pyridinium iodide of

TABLE I

Anils derived from β -naphthyl glyoxal hydrate and aromatic amines.

Anil	Colour	M.P.°C	Yield†	Formula	Nitrogen%	
					Calcd.	Found
R-Aniline	Yellow	96-97	90%	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO	5.40	5.36
R- <i>p</i> -toluidine	Brick red	90-92	92-93%	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO	5.12	5.00
R- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	Yellow	140-141	80%	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ NOCl	4.77	4.65
R- <i>m</i> -nitroaniline.	Yellow	98	70%	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	9.21	9.16
R- <i>p</i> -nitroaniline.	Yellow	123-124	72%	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	9.21	9.12
*R- α -naphthylamine.	Yellow	144-145	70%	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ NO	4.53	4.35
*R- β -naphthylamine.	Gummy mass	—	—	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ NO	—	—
R- <i>p</i> -dimethyl aminoaniline.	Reddish orange.	112-113	80%	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	9.27	9.21
R-nitrile <i>p</i> -dimethyl aminoaniline.	Dark red	140-141	90%	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O	12.84	12.78
R-C ₁₀ H ₇ COCH= (β -naphthacyl).						

*Slight warming was necessary.

β -naphthyl methyl ketone was dissolved in 10 ml of 50% ethanol and treated with 0.33 gm. of *p*-nitrosodimethyl aniline⁷ in 10.0 ml. ethanol. This was followed by the addition of 1.50 gm. of sodium cyanide in 4.0 ml water, maintaining a temperature of 20° throughout the

TABLE II

Characteristics of the derivatives of anils.

Anil	2:4-dinitrophenyl hydrazones			Semicarbazones			Oximes		
	M.P. °C	N% Calcd.	N% Found	M.P. °C	N% Calcd.	N% Found	M.P. °C	N% Calcd.	N% Found
R-Aniline	167 d	15.94	15.90	130-131	17.72	17.70	105-106	10.21	10.20
R- <i>p</i> -toluidine	172-173	15.45	15.42	150-152	16.96	16.89	123-124	9.72	9.59
R- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	130-131	14.78	14.71	110-111	15.97	15.93	117-118	9.07	9.00
R- <i>m</i> -nitroaniline	120-121	17.35	17.30	150-151	19.39	19.40	170-171	13.16	13.10
R- <i>p</i> -nitroaniline	150-151	17.35	17.32	135-136	19.39	19.36	190-192	13.16	13.13
R- α -naphthylamine	235d	14.31	14.29	210-212	15.30	15.19	153-155	8.64	8.61
R- β -naphthylamine	218-220	14.31	14.34	200-201	15.30	15.25	186-187	8.64	8.60
*R- <i>p</i> -dimethylamino anilic acid nitrile.	150-151	17.42	17.40	180-181	19.49	19.44	181-182	13.24	13.21
R- <i>p</i> -dimethyl aminoaniline acid nitrile.	250-252	19.32	19.30	131	21.87	21.82	145-146	16.37	16.34

R-C₁₀H₇COCH (β -naphthacyl)
d-decompose.

*No warming was necessary.

6. L. C. King, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 895.

7. A. I. Vogel, "A text book of Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 573, 1961, Longmans.

course of reaction. On addition of more water with subsequent chilling, scarlet red crystals of the anil were obtained *which could be crystallised from glacial acetic acid*, m.p. 140° (Table. I)

Derivative of Anils: 2 : 4-Dinitro phenylhydrazones, semicarbazones and the oximes of the anils were prepared by the usual methods and were obtained almost in theoretical yields. They were crystallised from hot alcohol. Characteristics of the derivatives are recorded in Table II.

TABLE III

Stretching frequencies of the functional groups of the anils.

Structure of anils.	CH=N cm. ⁻¹	C=O cm. ⁻¹	<i>p</i> -disubstituted groups cm. ⁻¹
1. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{-C}(\text{O})\text{=CH=N-C}_6\text{H}_5$	1580	1660	—
2. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{-C}(\text{O})\text{=CH=N-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-CH}_3$	1600	1660	820
3. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{-C}(\text{O})\text{=CH=N-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2$	1600	1640	840
4. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{-C}(\text{O})\text{=CH=N-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-Cl}$	1600	1650	830
5. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{-C}(\text{O})\text{=C}(\text{CN})\text{=N-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	1575	1680	825
6. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{-C}(\text{O})\text{=CH=N-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	1625	1660	830
7. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{-C}(\text{O})\text{=CH=N-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NO}_2$	1540	1640	827
8. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{-C}(\text{O})\text{=CH=N-C}_{10}\text{H}_7$	1610	1680	—

Infra-red spectra of Anils: In order to ascertain the functional groups of anils listed in Table I, their infra-red spectra were recorded in potassium bromide medium by Perkin-Elmer Infracord. The stretching frequencies of the groups are listed in Table III.

The stretching frequency of an aryl or a naphthyl ketone lies between 1695-1715 cm.⁻¹.⁸ Conjugation with respect to C=O, phenyl or naphthyl group generally decreased this frequency. Since the frequencies of the anils reported here are around the above range, it may be concluded that the anils possess a C=O group in the vicinity of β -naphthyl skeleton. Moreover the stretching frequency of C=N⁸ (unconjugated) lies between

8. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical applications of Infra red spectroscopy", 1963, Academic Press, New York and London.

1610-1700 cm^{-1} . The stretching frequencies of the anils range from 1540 to 1625 cm^{-1} . Evidence for the presence of C=N is therefore available. The lower value may again be due to conjugation. The frequency around 820-840 cm^{-1} may be due to *para* disubstituted derivative.

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